

On aeroacoustic space-time curvature for certain aerodynamic flows

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The research on acoustic metamaterials is probably the most lively research field in classical mechanics since the early achievements dating back to 2006. One of the most intriguing and challenging aspects emerged during the last decade deals with the theoretical modeling of the acoustic meta-behavior in presence of a background aerodynamic flow. Indeed, the structure of the equations governing the propagation of an acoustic perturbation in a moving medium is substantially different, due to the effect of the convective terms, mixing space and time derivatives through the components of the aerodynamic velocity vector field. An effective approach to cope with this aspect relies in the spacetime reinterpretation of the (aero)acoustic equations adopting the analytical tools developed within the framework of the special and general relativity. Indeed, the Minkowskian structure of the equations governing the propagation of waves in quiescent media turns out to be Lorentzian in presence of a non-uniform background aerodynamic, with the component of the velocity field acting as space-time-bending elements. The present paper analyses the actual structure of the aeroacoustic spacetime for certain types of flows of interest in many applications. The analysis will take advantage of the existence of analytical solutions to derive the structure of the metric tensor in closed form and make some consideration about the related Ricci's tensor and the corresponding scalar curvature. The paper will consider potential flows around simple geometries, including the effect of contact discontinuities (wakes), and potential vortices. The final goal of the research is a deeper understanding of the underlying structure of the acoustic spacetime for those classes of applications where the aerodynamic convection plays a key role, in order to contribute to the disclosure of breakthrough modeling approaches.

Keywords: aeroacoustic spacetime, spacetime curvature, Ricci's scalar

1. Introduction

While the end of 20th century was approaching, Matt Visser published a remarkable reinterpretation of the equation governing the propagation of an acoustic disturbance in presence of a background flow within the context of the Lorentzian differential geometry

(Visser [6][5]). The formal review of the convective wave equation within an aeroacoustic spacetime has unveiled a completely new perspective in the study of wave propagation phenomena where aerodynamic convection play a key role. This class of phenomena are of primary importance in many field of application and represent, in many cases, the leading challenge for researchers and designers. Nevertheless, Visser’s achievements initially suffered of a limited diffusion within the aeroacoustic community until the publication of the Analogue Transformation Acoustics (ATA) approach (Garcia Meca *et al.* [1] [2][3][4]), where the analytical tools of the Lorentzian differential geometry was used to develop a methodology for the design of acoustic metamaterials operating in a flow. According to Visser’s spacetime reformulation of the fundamental equations, the phenomenon of acoustic propagation reveals an underlying relativistic structure, where the aerodynamic velocity field plays the role of matter in general relativity. As a consequence, a non-uniform background velocity implies an underlying curvature of the acoustic spacetime continuum and represents the mechanism that induces the modification of the propagation patterns. In the present paper, the basic properties of of the aeroacoustic spacetime are analyzed for very simple flows for which the aerodynamic velocity is know analytically. Aim of the work is to contribute to the reinterpretation of the aeroacoustic equations within the Lorentzian context and to the development of novel tools for analysis and design in the field. A very brief review of the spacetime reformulation of the equations is given in Section 2, whereas the tools adopted in the measure of the spacetime curvature is presented in Section 3. The application of the concepts to simple potential flows is reported in Section 4.

2. The aeroacoustic spacetime

Aim of the present section is a quick review of the spacetime formulation of a problem of acoustic propagation within quiescent and moving media. The fundamentals of spacetime differential geometry are introduced without entering into details, addressing the interested reader to specific literature on the topic.

The standard notation adopted in special and general relativity is used throughout the paper. Specifically, Greek superscripts varying from 0 to 3 are used to indicate variables and operators defined in the four-dimensional spacetime, whereas Latin superscripts varying from 1 to 3 are used for the standard three-dimensional space. Einstein summation convention on repeated indices is used wherever applicable, unless otherwise specified. A spacetime *event* (*i.e.*, a “point” in the spacetime) is identified by the four-vector $\xi = (\xi^0, \xi^1, \xi^2, \xi^3) \equiv (c_0 t, x^i) \in \mathbb{R}^4$. It is worth repeating that c_0 must be considered as a dimensional, invariant scaling constant to ensure consistency with the fundamental assumptions of special relativity, and that no hypotheses on the nature of the medium or on its status are implied at this point. Indicating with $\partial_\mu = \partial/\partial\xi^\mu$ the covariant derivative with respect to ξ^μ , the four-gradient operator is the four-vector operator defined as $\partial = \partial_\nu g^\nu$, being g^ν an element of the contravariant basis. Let’s initially assume that our spacetime is a “flat” four-dimensional space, *i.e.*, a *Minkowski space*, that the ξ^α are a set of orthonormal, Cartesian-like coordinates. The separation of two events, P and Q , is denoted by the four-vector $\mathbf{u} = \xi_P - \xi_Q$ (see, *e.g.*, Carroll [7] for a rigorous and complete introduction to spacetime differential geometry). The spacetime interval s separating the

two events is given by

$$s^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu, \quad \text{with } \eta_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \vdots & 0 \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ 0 & \vdots & \delta_{ij} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

where $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the *Minkowski* metric tensor, having signature $(3, 1)$. One of the consequences of the structure of the Minkowski metric is that, in the spacetime context, covariant and contravariant basis vectors differ also for orthonormal coordinates on a flat manifold, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{g}^\nu = \eta^{\nu\mu} \mathbf{g}_\mu$, with $\eta^{\nu\mu} \eta_{\mu\gamma} = \delta_\gamma^\nu$. Within the spacetime context, the standard wave equation governing the propagation of the small fluctuations of the quantity φ within a quiescent medium can be expressed in the form

$$\partial_\mu (\eta^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \varphi) = \partial_\mu \partial^\nu \varphi = 0 \quad (2)$$

where the contravariant components of the four-gradient operator are related to the time and space derivatives by $(-\partial_0, \partial_1, \partial_2, \partial_3) = (-\partial_t/c_0, \partial_i)$. It is interesting to notice that Eq. 2 is written in conservation form. In presence of a background aerodynamic flow, the equation governing the propagation of a small perturbation of φ changes its form for the appearance of convective terms connecting the spacetime evolution of φ with the background aerodynamics. It can be easily shown (see *e.g.*, [8, 5, 11]) that the resulting convective wave equation can be recast in the form

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_\mu (\sqrt{-g} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \varphi) = 0 \quad (3)$$

i.e., the form of a generalized D'Alembertian on a Lorentzian (or *pseudo-Riemannian*) manifold with

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -(c_0^2 - v^2) & \vdots & -v_j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v_i & \vdots & \delta_{ij} \end{pmatrix}, \quad g^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{c_0^2} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \vdots & -v_j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v_i & \vdots & c_0^2 \delta_{ij} - v_i v_j \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The metric tensor has still signature $(3, 1)$, with $g < 0$ confirming the Lorentzian structure of the acoustic governing equations. The difference with respect to the case of a quiescent medium resides in the fact that the $g_{\mu\nu}$ and $g^{\mu\nu}$ are not diagonal and their component in general depend on $\boldsymbol{\xi}$, thus indicating that the spacetime where the acoustic propagation occurs is curve with curvature induced by the aerodynamic background field. In a certain way, we can think to aerodynamic convection in close analogy with the explanation of gravitation within the context of the general relativity. Indeed, according to the above reformulation, aerodynamic convection appears as an intrinsic property of the aeroacoustic spacetime, rather than a transport effect induced by the moving medium.

3. Measure of the spacetime curvature

The measure of the actual local curvature of the acoustic spacetime is not a trivial task even for the simplest velocity fields and becomes substantially unaffordable in real flows

involving distributed vorticity. Nevertheless, the possibility to explore how aerodynamics bends the spacetime for very simple flow models is, to the author's opinion, of some interest to gain a deeper insight in a large class of aeroacoustic problems. In the present work we will consider three simple potential velocity fields for which the spatial dependence is known analytically. Under this simplifying assumption, the extraction of information about the spacetime curvature is possible in a relatively simple way. The curvature of a (*pseudo*-)Riemannian manifold is completely described by the Riemann curvature tensor. For each event ξ , the Riemann tensor \mathbf{R} measures how much the metric tensor locally deviates from Euclidean isometry and has the form

$$R_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} = \partial_{\gamma}\Gamma_{\delta\beta}^{\alpha} - \partial_{\delta}\Gamma_{\gamma\beta}^{\alpha} + \Gamma_{\gamma\epsilon}^{\alpha}\Gamma_{\delta\beta}^{\epsilon} + \Gamma_{\delta\epsilon}^{\alpha}\Gamma_{\gamma\beta}^{\epsilon} \quad (5)$$

where the Christoffel symbols of the second type are related to the metric tensor as

$$\Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} = \mathbf{g}_{\alpha} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}^{\beta}}{\partial \xi^{\gamma}} = \frac{1}{2} g^{\alpha\lambda} (\partial_{\beta} g_{\gamma\lambda} + \partial_{\gamma} g_{\lambda\beta} - \partial_{\lambda} g_{\alpha\beta}) \quad (6)$$

As already mentioned, Riemann tensor comprises the whole information related to the curvature of the manifold. Nevertheless, its calculation and handling can be extremely difficult also for very simple spacetime geometries. We can reduce complexity, at the cost of a loss of information, by contracting the Riemann tensor w.r.t. the first and third indices

$$Ric_{\beta\delta} = R_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\gamma} \quad (7)$$

It is a measure of the local change in volume w.r.t. the Euclidean space. A further simplification can be obtained by contracting the Ricci tensor w.r.t. the metric tensor to obtain the scalar curvature, or Ricci scalar, $\mathcal{R} = g^{ij} Ric_{ij}$. Using the above definitions, the value of \mathcal{R} associated to the metrics 4 can be calculated as

$$R = \frac{1}{2c_0^2} \left[v_{1,3}^2 + v_{1,2}^2 + 4v_{1,1}^2 + 4v_1 v_{1,11} + 4v_{1,1} v_{2,2} + 2v_{1,2} v_{2,1} + 4v_{1,12} v_2 + \quad (8)$$

$$2v_{1,3} v_{3,1} + 4v_{1,1} v_{3,3} + 4v_{1,13} v_3 + 4v_1 v_{2,12} + 4v_1 v_{3,13} + v_{2,3}^2 + 4v_{2,2}^2 + \quad (9)$$

$$v_{2,1}^2 + 4v_2 v_{2,22} + 4v_{2,2} v_{3,3} + 2v_{2,3} v_{3,2} + 4v_{2,23} v_3 + 4v_2 v_{3,23} + 4v_{3,3}^2 + \quad (10)$$

$$v_{3,2}^2 + v_{3,1}^2 + 4v_3 v_{3,33} \quad (11)$$

where $v_{\mu,\nu}$ indicates the covariant derivative of v_{μ} with respect to ξ^{ν} . \mathcal{R} is the simplest invariant of the manifold and will be used in the following section to visualize the local curvature of the spacetime.

4. Sample applications

In the present section we apply the measure of the spacetime curvature to three simple background flows: the potential incompressible flow around a cylinder of unit radius at rest and rotating counterclockwise, and a synthetic shear layer mimicking a jet stream in a quiescent medium. In all cases the flow is assumed to be two-dimensional in the plane $\xi^1 \xi^2$, thus setting to zero all the derivative along ξ^3

In the first case, the background velocity field is induced by a uniform stream impinging an impermeable circular cylinder. It can be expressed analytically as the superposition of a uniform flow with velocity U aligned with ξ^1 and a doublet singularity located on the center of the cylinder section. The resulting velocity field is

$$v_1 = U \left(1 + \frac{1}{\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2} \right), \quad v_2 = \frac{-2U \xi^1 \xi^2}{(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2)^2} \quad (12)$$

Figure 1 shows the value of \mathcal{R} in the field calculated with Eq. 8. It is evident how the spacetime curvature increases approaching the cylinder. The latter represents the perturbation of the uniform stream responsible of the streamlines deviation associated to Eq. 12. Figure 2 depicts the streamlines of the total flow (left) and the vector field perturbation aerodynamic velocity (right). The curvature intensity follows the local intensity of the perturbation velocity. A similar behavior is observed if the cylinder is rotating

Figure 1: Local value of Ricci's scalar for a two-dimensional potential flow around a unit disk.

counterclockwise around its axis. The velocity field can be obtained from that induced by a cylinder at rest by adding a vortex singularity with intensity Γ located on the center of the cylinder section. The velocity components are given by

$$v_1 = U \left(1 + \frac{1}{\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2} \right) - \frac{\Gamma \xi^2}{2\pi (\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2)}, \quad v_2 = \frac{-2U \xi^1 \xi^2}{(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2)^2} + \frac{\Gamma \xi^1}{2\pi (\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2)} \quad (13)$$

The curvature of the aeroacoustic continuum follows also in this case the intensity of the perturbation velocity. The spatial distribution is not symmetric, according to the properties of the flow, and goes to zero on the sector of the cylinder where the boundary moves against the incoming flow. In Figure 4 it is evident how the velocity field vectors are aligned with isolevels of the the scalar curvature, confirming the above considerations.

The third test case is one of the benchmarks proposed in [12] (specifically, problem no. 1/category 4) slightly modified here to introduce a streamwise variation of the shear layer section. The velocity field is given by

$$v_1 = U 2^{[-\xi^{2^2}/(b+\alpha\xi^1)^2]}, \quad v_2 = \alpha v_1 \frac{\xi^2}{b + \alpha \xi^1} \quad (14)$$

Figure 2: Streamlines of the total velocity field (left) and the perturbation velocity (right) superimposed to the Ricci's scalar map for a two-dimensional potential flow around a unit disk.

Figure 3: Local value of Ricci's scalar for a two-dimensional potential flow around a rotating unit disk.

The corresponding distribution of \mathcal{R} is presented in Fig. 5. In this case, the intensity of the aerodynamic velocity has a local maximum at $y = 0$ and presents the sharper variations at a values of y varying with the streamwise coordinate. This behavior affects directly the scalar curvature that presents a peak along the y direction corresponding to the stronger variation of v . The analysis of the streamlines associated with 14 and the iso-level curves of the velocity magnitude (Fig. 6) confirm the observation, showing that the highest curvature occur at the highest velocity gradients. These considerations can be used as a starting point for the reinterpretation of the acoustic propagation within moving media using a novel point of view, where the aerodynamic velocity field can be seen as an intrinsic property of the aeroacoustic spacetime, providing additional tools of insight for researchers and designers.

Figure 4: Streamlines of the total velocity field (left) and the perturbation velocity (right) superimposed to the Ricci's scalar map for a potential flow around a rotating unit disk.

Figure 5: Local value of Ricci's scalar for benchmark problem no. 1/Cat. 4 from [12] (modified).

5. Conclusions

The curvature of the aeroacoustic spacetime in presence of certain types of flow has been analysed using the standard tools of the Lorentzian differential geometry. The dependence of the curvature on the spatial variations of the background aerodynamics has been derived analytically evaluating the trace of the Ricci tensor \mathcal{R} for a general case of steady, non-uniform flow. The numerical assessment has been performed on three simple flows for which the velocity field is known analytically. In all cases, the numerical simulations show how the entity of the spacetime curvature depends on the local variations of the aerodynamic field. The background velocity of the medium can be thus interpreted as an intrinsic property of the aeroacoustic spacetime, similarly to the reinterpretation of the role of matter within the general relativity context. The purpose of the present research is to investigate on this specific aspect, in order to contribute to the establishment of a novel

Figure 6: Streamlines of the total velocity field (left) and contour levels of the velocity magnitude (right) superimposed to the Ricci's scalar map for benchmark problem no. 1/Cat. 4 from [12] (modified).

point of view in the interpretation of the aeroacoustic phenomena and the development of innovative tools for analysis and design.

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